

1 **Smoothed millennial-scale palaeoclimatic reference data as unconventional comparison targets:**
2 **Application to European loess records**

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20 **Abstract:**

21 Millennial-scale palaeoclimate variability has been documented in various terrestrial and marine
22 palaeoclimate proxy records throughout the Northern Hemisphere for the last glacial cycle. Its clear
23 expression and rapid shifts between different states of climate (Greenland Interstadials and Stadials)
24 represents a correlation tool beyond the resolution of e.g. luminescence dating, especially relevant for
25 terrestrial deposits. Usually, comparison of terrestrial proxy datasets and the Greenland ice cores
26 indicates a complex expression of millennial-scale climate variability as recorded in terrestrial
27 geoarchives including loess. Loess is the most widespread terrestrial geoarchive of the Quaternary and
28 especially widespread over Eurasia. However, loess often records a smoothed representation of
29 millennial-scale variability without all fidelity when compared to the Greenland data, this being a
30 relevant limiting feature in integrating loess with other palaeoclimate records.

31 To better understand the loess proxy-response to millennial-scale climate variability, we simulate a
32 proxy signal smoothing by natural processes through application of low-pass filters of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ data from
33 Greenland, a high-resolution palaeoclimate reference record, alongside speleothem isotope records
34 from the Black Sea-Mediterranean region. We show that low-pass filters represent rather simple
35 models for better constraining the expression of millennial-scale climate variability in low
36 sedimentation environments, and in sediments where proxy-response signals are most likely affected
37 by natural smoothing (by e.g. bioturbation).

38 Interestingly, smoothed datasets from Greenland and the Black Sea-Mediterranean region are most
39 similar in the last ~15 ka and between ~50-30 ka. Between ~30-15 ka, roughly corresponding to the
40 Last Glacial Maximum and the deglaciation, the records show dissimilarities, challenging the
41 construction of robust correlative time-scales in this age range. From our analysis it becomes apparent
42 that patterns of palaeoclimate signals in loess-palaeosol sequences often might be better explained by
43 smoothed Greenland reference data than the original high-resolution Greenland dataset, or other
44 reference data. This opens the possibility to better assess the temporal resolution and palaeoclimate
45 potential of loess-palaeosol sequences in recording supra-regional climate patterns, as well as to
46 securely integrate loess with other chronologically better-resolved palaeoclimate records.

47 **1. Introduction**

48 **1.1. Millennial-scale climate variability**

49 Millennial-scale climate variability, namely the Greenland Interstadials (GI) and Stadials (GS) is
50 documented in ice-core, marine and speleothem records from the Northern Hemisphere during the
51 last glacial cycle. These rapid palaeoclimate events (GI and GS) induced changes in the terrestrial
52 environments on land^{e.g. 1-10}. However, for most palaeoclimate records the synchronicity of change is
53 hard to establish due to dating uncertainties and different sensitivity to past climate forcing¹¹⁻¹³.
54 Increasing the analytical resolution does not necessarily solve these issues, and a recent study¹⁴ argues
55 that “discrepancies remain in the temporal development of rapid climate change for specific events”.

56 **1.2. Low-pass filters and their properties**

57 Low-pass filters are a way of omitting high-frequency oscillations of a particular dataset and focusing
58 on the low-frequency (long wavelength) part of the signal. Before filtering, datasets are linearly
59 interpolated. The interpolation resolution will determine the number of data points, and the process
60 can change the auto-correlation of datasets. It needs to be mentioned that filters, as also other time
61 series analyses techniques, commonly have edge effects^{e.g. 15,16} at the beginning and end of datasets.
62 In practice, this means that filters may not reliably represent data at the beginning and end of datasets.
63 Therefore, the patterns of filters around these intervals should not be interpreted in detail.

64 Smoothing of noisy data is a basic principle of data and signal processing allowing for the extraction of
65 longer-term patterns and avoidance of high-frequency fluctuations, which may represent noise¹⁷.
66 While the mean of moving windows smooth data directly, filters focus on specific frequency ranges.
67 Low-pass filters extract the long-term variability of a dataset and exclude the high-frequency content.
68 Band pass filters are widely used to extract information about specific frequency components
69 especially of orbital climate forcing^{e.g. 18-22}. Low-pass filters have been used to focus on the low
70 frequency components of solar²³, millennial²⁴ and orbital^{e.g. 25-28} signals with implications in defining
71 past climate variability. Although the concept of low-pass filters is similar to a moving average (see
72 Fig. 1 for a comparison of two examples), filters have the advantage that the frequency response can
73 be constrained by adjusting the roll-off rate, a parameter for the width of the frequency response of
74 filters. This feature makes filters a powerful tool, especially when flexibility in their design (cut-off
75 frequencies and roll off rate) is provided. This is the case for Taner filters as implemented in the
76 ‘astrochron’ R package²⁹⁻³¹. Here, Taner low-pass filters are used to investigate smoothed signals in ice
77 cores and speleothems, as approximation/representation/simulation for smoothing due to e.g.

78 loessification (post-depositional alteration including weak pedogenesis) combined with low
79 sedimentation rates^{e.g. 32,33} for loess records.

80 **1.3. Loess proxy records and their chronologies on millennial time scales**

81 Loess records form one of the most widespread terrestrial palaeoclimate archives in the mid latitudes
82 of Northern Hemisphere landmasses^{e.g. 34–37}. Limitations induced by proxy-response time, thresholds
83 and tipping points often result in smoothing of the primary climate signal by syn- and post-sedimentary
84 bioturbation and/or chemical weathering. Therefore, a uniform understanding of loess palaeoclimate
85 data in the light of millennial-scale past climate variability is not always well constrained, albeit
86 patterns of millennial-scale climate variability can be identified in many records^{e.g. 4,12,13,38,39}. It is
87 important to note that different processes can be expected to act on different depth- and time scales.
88 Bioturbation can range from mm to decimetre-scale burrows. In addition, dissolution in the
89 underground including sinkholes can appear and disturb the stratigraphy. The depth and intensity of
90 soil formation will depend on amongst others the vegetation type. Therefore, our approach of
91 smoothing a record needs to be considered a simplification trying to sum all smoothing mechanisms,
92 which in reality act on different depth and time scales.

93 As millennial-scale climate variability has been documented in various Eurasian records^{e.g. 1,4,5,10,39–48}, it
94 can be expected that its imprint would be discernible also in low-resolution loess records.

95 **1.4. Chronologies for loess geoarchives: Dating and correlation**

96 Constraining reliable chronologies for loess records beyond radiocarbon dating is especially
97 challenging because of considerable uncertainty of luminescence dating techniques, the main methods
98 applicable to dating the emplacement time of mineral-particles forming loess^{e.g. 49–52}. Their precision
99 and accuracy is often unable to provide the dating resolution needed for unambiguous assignment of
100 palaeoclimatic signals to reference datasets such as independently dated ice cores^{53–56} or speleothem
101 data^{e.g. 1,6,9}. This commonly leaves inferred correlation of supposedly (quasi)identical past climate
102 events as the only method to establish high-resolution chronologies for loess. However, several loess
103 proxy-data show less high-frequency oscillations on millennial time scales than high-resolution
104 reference records^{e.g. 57–61}, challenging detailed pattern-matching attempts. To counter this issue at
105 least partly, we suggest to smooth (technically: low-pass filter) high-resolution reference data^{e.g.1,54,62}
106 before attempting comparison and correlation of palaeoclimate events among loess records or
107 between loess and other palaeoclimate archives. This is expected to facilitate the comparison of
108 datasets with similar temporal resolution leading to a better understanding of proxy-response and
109 palaeoclimate potential of such records.

110 Correlative age models relying on the identification of similar patterns in loess and well established
111 reference records could provide more reliable age-depth relationships especially when verified by
112 independently dated tie-points such as tephra layers^{3,12,63–65}. Correlative age models have proven
113 crucial for time scale development especially on orbital and millennial time scales^{e.g. 66–68}. Prominently
114 orbital tuning, magnetostratigraphy and also isotope- and event stratigraphy are based on visual or
115 signal correlation, though often supported by an integrated stratigraphic approach using several
116 independent dating techniques^{69–73}. Although correlative age models may be regarded as reliable
117 geochronometric methods^{71,74,75}, correlation may impose artificial patterns in data series^{28,76–80}.

118 Further, such time scales may be hardly reproducible and are often based on individual choice and
119 experience. Several methods have been developed to overcome or limit ambiguities and allow for a
120 more quantitative assessment of correlations, age models and their significance^{28,29,77,80–87}. It may be
121 regarded acceptable that correlation is most reliable when supplemented and supported by
122 independent age control. Correlative age models and comparisons have been widely applied to loess
123 research^{e.g. 4,39,88–96}, and many time scales older than the last glacial cycle are at least partly based on
124 correlation to other geoarchives, usually marine or ice cores^{54,97,98} or orbital correlation targets⁹⁹. As
125 demonstrated for radiometric time scales¹⁰⁰, also correlative time scales can be expected to provide
126 unreliable constraints where no clear data patterns can be traced between records, or no tie points
127 can be set without ambiguity. Especially because even large numbers of radiometric dates can hardly
128 prove synchrony of events between records, we regard correlation besides dating of vital importance
129 for improving loess palaeoenvironmental reconstructions.

130 2. Results

131 Results for the low-pass filtering of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ data from Greenland are performed in 1 ka steps of the cut-
132 off period from 1-15 ka (and thus the cut-off frequency of 1/2 to 1/15 [1/ka]; Fig. 2). While the filtering
133 with cut-off periods of 1-2 ka indicates prominent millennial-scale climate variability, these patterns
134 vanish with increasing cut-off frequency, and give way to patterns of several ka periods (cut-off period
135 \sim 4-8 ka) to orbital scale variability (cut-off period $>$ 10 ka).

136 The visual and quantified comparison of the Greenland $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ data on the AICC2012 time scale⁵⁶ and
137 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ data from Sofular cave in northern Turkey¹ suggests general similarity, but dissimilarity is also
138 observable especially in the interval from \sim 30-15 ka (Fig. 3). The similarity of these datasets is especially
139 high for the last \sim 15 ka and the time interval from \sim 40-30 ka. Correlation among those two reference
140 records exceeds the significance at 95% confidence for cut-off frequencies of 15 ka (Fig. 3, top panel)
141 for the last \sim 15 ka. In contrary, the time interval from \sim 25-15 ka shows little variability in the ice core
142 record, a gap in the speleothem dataset, and generally pattern amplitudes are low (Fig. 3), resulting in
143 no significant relationship.

144 Next, magnetic susceptibility data from Chinese and European loess^{61,101–105} (Fig.4) reveal for Marine
145 Isotope Stage (MIS) 3 a soil formation phase mainly characterized by three prominent maxima in the
146 magnetic susceptibility records. These are difficult to explain by simple comparison to insolation and
147 the Imbrie and Imbrie (1980) ice model (Fig. 4).

148 In Fig. 5, the smoothed Greenland record is compared to the Rb/K ratio, a loess weathering proxy from
149 the Bíňa section in the Czech Republic¹⁰⁷. The comparison shows that some intervals are highly
150 smoothed in the proxy dataset (especially the part younger ca. 40 ka), and that especially the time
151 interval around 60 ka is expressed very well in the proxy record. The available time scale, based on a
152 combination of luminescence dating and correlation to Greenland $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ data¹⁰⁷, may be refined by
153 comparison and correlation to a smoothed Greenland signal. In particular, when compared to a suite
154 of smoothed correlation targets, one can assess which of these resembles the variability in the proxy
155 dataset best.

156 A loess-palaeosol record from Rasova at the Lower Danube¹² spanning the last 45 ka, which records
157 millennial-scale climate variability in various proxy data including the frequency dependent magnetic

158 susceptibility, is investigated regarding its (dis)similarity with a low-pass filtered Greenland signal. As
159 for the comparison between Greenland $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and Sofular cave $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, the similarity is high for the time
160 intervals from $\sim 40\text{-}30$ ka and $\sim 15\text{-}0$ ka, while less similar in the interval from $\sim 30\text{-}15$ ka. For Rasova, the
161 occurrence of the Campanian Ignimbrite/Y-5 tephra dated at ~ 40 ka¹⁰⁸, often found in the Lower
162 Danube loess records as a chronostratigraphic marker⁶⁵, complicates signal comparison around 40 ka
163 because of its considerable thickness (see Fig. 6). Furthermore, the high magnetic susceptibility signal
164 related to this tephra, and tailing for ca. 1 ka towards younger ages, is therefore clearly not only an
165 palaeoenvironmental signal.

166 **3. Discussion**

167 **3.1. Technical aspects of smoothing and comparison**

168 Smoothing of reference datasets, here in steps of 1 kyr, allows for a detailed comparison in several
169 examples (Figs. 1, 2, 5, 6), while in some cases (Figs. 3, 4) longer steps such as 3 kyr are useful as well.
170 Comparison is done in a qualitative way in this study. Here, the aim is obtaining a better understanding
171 of millennial-scale climate variability in European terrestrial records, and the visual comparison in Figs.
172 2-6 is a powerful tool for this purpose.

173 In order to statistically test observed similarities, it is possible to calculate windowed correlation
174 coefficients. However, this is only useful when no (or little) flexibility in the time domain is present,
175 which is not the case for these examples. Often it is necessary to apply quantitative correlation
176 analyses. In our opinion, the application of phase randomized surrogates^{29,30,81,82} is the most suitable
177 way of quantifying significance, and we apply it here. We include selected overlapping moving window
178 correlations with moving window widths equivalent to the cut-off frequency (see Figs. 3, 6) to support
179 our findings. Note that both the window length and the data resolution are factors influencing
180 correlation and significance tests. For technical details, see the methods section and the computer
181 code in supplementary materials. See also⁹³ for a critical discussion of correlating loess proxy datasets.

182 Edge effects of filters are not particularly prominent in the shown examples, but such effects can be
183 seen e.g. at the old end of data displayed in Fig. 1, and at the young end of the filters in Fig. 2. In this
184 case, filters suggest rather low values at the young end of the dataset, which is clearly not suggested
185 by the dataset itself.

186 **3.2. Smoothing of palaeoenvironmental signals in terrestrial sedimentary records**

187 It is a well-known fact that many sedimentary geoarchives record a smoothed representation of past
188 climate variations^{111, and references therein}. Reasons are multifold and include low deposition rates, chemical,
189 physical and biological mixing processes^{e.g. 112–115}, as well as low sampling resolution. Note that while
190 these processes will act on different time scales and possibly with different time-delay to climate
191 forcing, the here discussed filtering process represents a simplified model of the sum of these. Aeolian
192 sediments can be expected to preserve a record of climate forcing over a considerable time span. Soil
193 formation including (physical and chemical) weathering processes will act on varying depths,
194 depending on the (climate driven) intensity of processes, and are modulated by deposition rates of
195 aeolian material. Various processes contribute to a signal smoothing in terrestrial environments, and
196 although several possible processes can be named, the complex interplay of these can be expected to

197 be site specific. In practice, rather smooth sedimentary datasets are sometimes considered indicative
198 for continuous deposition. Also final accumulation (and preservation) rates are depending on the
199 depositional environment. Strong variability in proxy data with depth may be interpreted as either
200 different sediment sources or variable local environmental conditions. Gaps in the sedimentary record
201 pose a challenge for all depth/time series analyses methods. Here we assume a quasi-continuous
202 sedimentation on millennial time scale, which exist^{e.g. 4,39}. Where this is not the case, and erosion
203 and/or colluvial sediments are present, care must be taken not to interpret resulting features as
204 palaeoclimate patterns.

205 **3.3. Comparison to smoothed reference datasets improves interpretations of proxy records**

206 We advocate considering smoothed signals as comparison targets for geoarchives with different
207 temporal resolutions and discuss this approach in the context of comparing low-pass filters of e.g. the
208 high-resolution Greenland and Sofular records to terrestrial loess deposits. We clearly do not
209 recommend this approach to answer research questions of timing, synchronicity (lead and lags) and
210 duration of millennial-scale climate variability when no additional data is available. We do introduce
211 this approach as a useful way to assess chronological correlations and to obtain an overview of how
212 smoothed studied records may look like. All here discussed datasets show different imprints of
213 millennial-scale climate variability, which would have influenced all discussed proxy datasets, and may
214 have imposed palaeoenvironmental (and therefore data) variability in the period band of 2-15 ka. This
215 period range in between orbital- and millennial time scales is often difficult to use for comparison (and
216 correlation) of palaeoclimate proxies. This is due to the absence of reference datasets showing a clear
217 variability in this period band.

218 Fig. 4 shows selected low-pass filters for the Greenland $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ data, the Imbrie and Imbrie (1980) ice
219 model as parametrized by Lisiecki and Raymo (2005), and also the orbital parameters precession and
220 obliquity⁹⁹ for the last 130 ka. Differences in timing of the filter maxima representing the warmest
221 phase of MIS 3 according to the discussed reference records are apparent and range from ~60 to ~52
222 ka. This makes an unambiguous and precise correlation challenging, where it is not clear which of these
223 reference datasets is most suitable. Especially the similar pattern but different timing of Northern
224 Hemisphere insolation and the Imbrie and Imbrie (1980) ice model allow for ambiguity. Several loess
225 datasets record three clear intervals reflecting rather warm and relatively humid climatic conditions
226 during MIS 3^{e.g. 116}. Such a pattern is not found in insolation- or ice models, but it is observed in the
227 smoothed Greenland data (Fig. 4, red arrows). A good relation between the soil complexes related to
228 MIS 3 and their magnetic susceptibility signal and a smoothed Greenland $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ signal can be achieved
229 (Fig. 4), especially when low-pass filtering the original record with a cut-off period of (around) 9 ka.
230 Especially for MIS 3, the low-pass filters may therefore be useful correlation targets, particularly where
231 the resolution of geoarchives is in between millennial and orbital time scales. In several time intervals
232 (~40-30 ka, ~15-0 ka) loess data can be correlated more clearly to low-pass filters of Greenland isotope
233 data than to other reference datasets (Fig. 4). This comparison allows therefore for an interpretation
234 regarding the timing of the MIS 3 soil formation, and its dominant forcing.

235 A last glacial weathering proxy dataset from the Czech Republic in loess and loess-like sediments¹⁰⁷
236 shows varying weathering intensity and changing sedimentation rates¹⁰⁷ (Fig. 5). We compare this
237 dataset to Greenland $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ data and its smoothed representations. The comparison allows for assigning

238 different resolutions of the acquired palaeoenvironmental signal, related to changes in sedimentation
239 rate. In this case, a rather high recording resolution of ~ 1 ka around 60 ka can be inferred, which
240 decreases to ~ 2 -3 ka from ~ 55 -40 ka, and thereafter is in the order of ~ 5 ka. This example demonstrates
241 that a comparison to different low-pass filtered reference data allows an improved proxy data
242 understanding, which may be used for time scale evaluation and construction.

243 As a third example, we use a loess profile from the Lower Danube¹² (Fig. 6). Some maxima in the
244 (frequency dependent) magnetic susceptibility around 40-30 ka are similar to the smoothed Greenland
245 reference data and indicate a recording resolution of ~ 1 ka. Thereafter, the similarity between
246 Greenland reference data and the loess archive becomes less obvious until the beginning of the
247 Holocene, which can be assessed visually or via correlation analysis. This, in combination with the
248 comparison of Greenland and Sofular cave data, may suggest an interpretation that the Black Sea
249 region was strongly linked to the Northern Hemisphere climate evolution (here approximated by the
250 Greenland reference dataset) at least until ca. 30 ka, and thereafter the link to Greenland and Sofular
251 cave may have been weaker. In this case, correlation is mostly significant above 95% confidence level
252 until around 35 ka, and from ca. 25 ka towards present.

253 **3.4. Smoothed reference datasets as correlation templates, with focus on the last glacial cycle and** 254 **MIS 3 in European loess**

255 In addition to the use for an improved understanding of proxy records, the low-pass filtered reference
256 datasets^{1,54} may be employed as correlation targets. The comparison of (terrestrial) proxy data
257 (challenging to independently date) to smoothed reference datasets may allow assigning a time scale
258 through correlation, ideally backed up by independent chronological data.

259 We show that correlation of palaeoclimate proxy data from MIS 3 is especially challenging when
260 millennial-scale variability is not clearly identifiable in proxy-data and cannot be used to establish a
261 reliable time scale (e.g. Fig. 4). In such cases, independent dating may point to a match to precession,
262 ice models or a smoothed Greenland signal. We show several cases^{107,116,117} where patterns are best
263 explained by a smoothed Greenland signal, and considerable mismatches to all 'classical' correlation
264 targets exist. The (palaeoenvironmental) interpretation of other loess datasets may benefit from
265 similar comparisons to reference datasets between millennial and orbital scales.

266 The here presented examples come from terrestrial loess geoarchives covering the last glacial cycle.
267 As expected, our analysis shows that the palaeoclimate proxy signal was not recorded with a constant
268 temporal resolution. We find that some palaeoclimatic and/or sedimentary conditions can facilitate
269 the recording of a clear palaeoenvironmental signal. This is to be kept in mind for correlations in
270 general, and especially when interpreting weak signals with low variability.

271 **4. Conclusions**

272 Here we discuss a new approach in defining low-pass filters with changing cut-off frequencies from
273 well dated high-resolution reference records of millennial-scale climate variability for the last glacial
274 cycle^{1,54}. The results can exemplarily explain proxy datasets with less established time control better
275 than the use of commonly applied high-resolution reference datasets. This improved correlation is

276 proposed to allow for a better understanding of proxy datasets, and possibly more reliable correlative
277 age models, which are especially powerful when supported by independent and reliable dating.

278 We propose using low-pass filtered reference records when palaeoclimate datasets show variability
279 between millennial and orbital scales, and no other suitable reference datasets are available. Applying
280 this approach, we

281 (a) explain observed patterns and their relation to millennial-scale climate variability in several
282 terrestrial examples,

283 (b) can gain insight in the temporal resolution of geoarchives, and

284 (c) propose these filtered/smoothed signals as correlation targets for records lacking high frequency
285 (millennial-scale) recording but showing smoothed climate variability on supra-millennial-scales (~2-
286 15ka).

287 Moreover, low-pass filters as a simplified model improve our understanding how low sedimentation,
288 bioturbation, and pedogenesis may result in a smoothing of terrestrial (loess) records.

289 In our opinion, comparing smoothed records to reference data may be a step forward especially for
290 last glacial stratigraphies, where millennial-scale patterns may be expected, but are not directly
291 recorded in full resolution in some (marine, lacustrine, terrestrial) geoarchives.

292 **5. Methods**

293 **5.1. Filter settings**

294 Filtering is done here using a Taner filter as implemented in the ‘astrochron’ R package^{29–31}. More
295 details on Taner filters are available in¹¹⁸ and supplementary materials. We use several cut-off
296 frequencies in 1- ka steps, from 1 to 15. The roll-off rate is set to 10²⁰ for all filters; it determines the
297 spectral filter response. An exemplary sensitivity analysis of the roll-off rate is provided in the
298 supplementary materials. Different settings of the roll-off rate are expected to lead to similar results
299 and can be tested using the appended R scripts. Note that we use a single filtering step for processes
300 acting on different time scales. Although we consider this an improvement it is a simplification at the
301 same time.

302 **5.2. Reference datasets and European terrestrial context**

303 Here, we low-pass filter several high-resolution reference records on their individual age models,
304 which show high-frequency oscillations on millennial time scales (Figs. 2, 3). We use the Greenland
305 $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ data^{54,55} on the AICC2012^{55,56} time scale, and the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ datasets from Sofular cave¹ in the Black Sea
306 area. Greenland $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ is commonly regarded as a proxy dataset for past temperature variability over
307 Greenland, possibly representative for the North Atlantic or northern hemisphere temperature
308 evolution⁵⁴. However, it also represents the most commonly used palaeoclimate and chronological
309 reference dataset for disentangling past climate variability during the last glacial cycle in the Northern
310 Hemisphere^{2,3,12,13,39,119–123}. The Sofular cave $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ dataset¹ represents a reliably and independently
311 U/Th dated terrestrial cave record that would allow for direct comparison with (south-eastern)
312 European loess deposits. This is because the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ isotopic composition of cave calcite is climate-driven

313 by hydroclimatic processes directly affecting the soil and vegetation composition above the cave¹ and
314 thus provide a direct analogue to biogeochemical processes affecting loess records.

315 Taner low-pass filters are used as correlation target and compared to several geoscientific datasets:
316 (a) Two rock magnetic loess records covering the last glacial cycle from Mošorin/Serbia in the
317 Carpathian Basin¹¹⁶, and the magnetic susceptibility stack from the Loess Plateau in China¹¹⁷ (Fig. 4);
318 (b) a weathering proxy dataset from partly pedogenetically overprinted loess at Biňa/Slovakia¹⁰⁷ (Fig.
319 5); and (c) a rock magnetic dataset from Rasova/Romania in the Lower Danube Basin^{12,124} (Fig. 6). These
320 datasets have been chosen for several reasons. The datasets of magnetic susceptibility from loess
321 (Serbian dataset and Chinese loess stack) spanning the last glacial cycle^{116,117} are investigated to
322 demonstrate issues in comparing loess data to insolation data⁹⁹ and the ice model by Imbrie and Imbrie
323 (1980). These datasets demonstrate the usefulness of smoothed millennial-scale records in
324 interpreting the patterns found in terrestrial geoarchives. The Rb/K weathering record¹⁰⁷ is used here
325 for demonstrating the potential of obtaining a better understanding of loess (like) records as
326 palaeoclimate archives on millennial-scale by comparison to both a high-resolution proxy record (here:
327 the Greenland isotope record), and also its smoothed representations following different cut-off
328 frequencies. Finally, the datasets from the loess record from Rasova in the Lower Danube Basin on its
329 individual time scale established by a combination of luminescence dating, tephrochronology and
330 correlation¹² is used to show how avoiding noisy high-frequency components can help interpreting
331 these records in respect to both hemispheric-scale and/or more local palaeoclimate influences. The
332 code of computations associated with this manuscript is available in supplementary materials.

333 Classical and often used reference datasets in palaeoclimatic comparisons and (chronological)
334 correlations include Northern Hemisphere summer insolation⁹⁹, and the Imbrie and Imbrie (1980)¹¹¹
335 ice model as parametrized for an oxygen isotope stack⁹⁸. The (frequency dependent) magnetic
336 susceptibility from loess-palaeosol records is commonly used as proxy for inferring the degree of
337 pedogenetic overprinting of aeolian material, which is largely controlled by temperature and especially
338 moisture availability¹⁰⁴. Proxy data from the Chinese Loess Plateau and European loess belt¹⁰¹⁻¹⁰⁵ show
339 that loess magnetic susceptibility is a reliable proxy for inferring palaeoenvironmental conditions and
340 associated palaeoenvironmental change through time.

341 **5.3. Correlation analysis**

342 Correlation can be computed through the calculation of correlation coefficients for linear and
343 nonlinear systems^{e.g. 109,110}, here we use the Spearman rank correlation coefficient for quantification of
344 similarity. Using classical statistics to calculate the significance of the correlation is not plausible here
345 since the data are serially correlated. In our opinion, the application of phase randomized
346 surrogates^{29,30,81,82} is the most suitable way of quantifying significance. This method is applied as
347 implemented in the 'astrochron' R package^{29,30}. Here, we compare correlation coefficients to moving
348 window significant levels of correlation (Figs 3, 6). For more details, please see the computer code in
349 supplementary materials.

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360 **Author contributions**

361 All authors (CZ, IO, DV, SKB, JH, SBM, JB, FL, CR, UH) contributed significantly to the science, manuscript
362 writing and internal discussions. CZ and IO had the idea for the study and designed the study. CZ
363 implemented all calculations. Discussion of methods and results was done jointly by all authors. All
364 authors (CZ, IO, DV, SKB, JH, SBM, JB, FL, CR, UH) read and carefully went through a manuscript two
365 times, which led to the submitted version. Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Comparison of low-pass filters (orange) and moving averages (blue), example 1

Comparison of low-pass filters (orange) and moving averages (blue), example 2

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653 Figure 1: Comparison of low-pass filters (orange) and moving averages (blue) on two artificial datasets.

654 An example of a highly auto-correlated signal (top; auto-correlation coefficient 0.9), and a less auto-
655 correlated and 'more noisy' signal (bottom; auto-correlation coefficient 0.5). Note that especially for
656 the second (noisier) example filters focus more on longer-term trends and are less affected by high-
657 frequency signals, which may represent noise. From bottom to top the moving average window width
658 and cut-off frequency increases from 1 to 14 scale units.

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661 2: Low-pass filters with cut-off frequencies from 1-14 ka (increasing from bottom to top) of the
662 Greenland $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ record, a record often used as correlation target for last glacial northern hemisphere
663 climate evolution. All data were standardized, and low-pass filters are offset on the ordinate for
664 plotting. Note the increasing smoothness with increasing cut-off frequency (bottom to top, from 1-14).

665
 666 Figure 3: Comparison of two independently dated reference datasets for Europe and the Black Sea
 667 region: Greenland $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ data and its smoothing by low-pass filtering (blue; cut-off period is indicated
 668 at the right from 4-12 a), and the Solfular cave $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ data (black) data and low-pass filters with cut-off
 669 frequencies of 3, 6, 9, 12 and 15 ka (see numbers at the right). Note general similarity, and dissimilarity
 670 especially between ~ 30 and 15 ka. Spearman rank correlation coefficients for the filters with cut-off
 671 frequencies at 3, 9, and 15 kyr are included (red), they each have axes on the right. The top panel
 672 include results of a correlation test (green; see chapters 3.1 and 5.3), correlation is significant where
 673 correlation of the dataset (red) is higher than for reference (green); this is the case from ~ 20 ka until
 674 present for the data filtered with a cut-off frequency of 15 kyr. Selected low-pass filters were used for
 675 correlation and significance to keep the figure clear.

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678 Figure 4: Original- and low-pass filters of Greenland $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ data (bottom), compared with other
 679 established reference datasets from the last glacial cycle, and two datasets from loess. Reference
 680 datasets represent the ice model¹⁰⁶, parametrized as for a marine benthic isotope stack⁹⁸, summer
 681 insolation at 65°N⁹⁹, and an ETP mix of eccentricity, tilt (obliquity) and precession⁹⁹. Loess datasets
 682 from the Carpathian Basin (Mošorin/Serbia)¹¹⁶ and China¹¹⁷ are displayed at the top. Please note a 3-
 683 division of enhanced magnetic susceptibility, which cannot be explained by classical correlation
 684 targets, but by a smoothed Greenland signal.

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Figure 5: Comparison of the Rb/K signal from the Bína profile (luminescence dated)¹⁰⁷ and low-pass filtered Greenland $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ data. Note the different resolution recorded in the sequence. The higher resolution at the base is a consequence of its geomorphologic position in a depression, which was filled with sediment. Consequently, the top of the sequence has lower deposition rates, and also a lower recorded resolution. Vertical correlation lines after the original luminescence-supported correlation in¹⁰⁷. Red arrows propose correlation of the signal to differently smoothed Greenland records.

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694 Figure 6: Comparison of Greenland $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ data and its smoothing by low-pass filters (blue), with data of
 695 the frequency dependent magnetic susceptibility from Rasova at the Lower Danube¹² (black).
 696 Correlation is quantified via the Spearman rank correlation to allow for some nonlinearity, and is
 697 included for three low-pass filters s in red. This selection is made to keep the figure clear. Significance
 698 is evaluated as well, and correlation for phase-randomized surrogates as reference is plotted in green.
 699 Correlation is significant where the data correlation (red) is higher than reference correlation (green).
 700 Note similarity especially in the intervals from ~ 38 - 30 ka (red arrows), and dissimilarity especially
 701 between ca. 15 and 30 ka. Note likely distortion of the loess signal at ~ 40 - 39 ka due to occurrence of a
 702 tephra layer related to the Campanian Ignimbrite (CI, red box).

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